

Full Length Research Paper

An outbreak of avian influenza in a flock of 19 weeks old isa brown layer chickens: A CASE REPORT

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Three (3) carcasses and one (1) live chicken were presented at the Avian Clinic of the Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto from a flock of 956 19-week old Isa brown layers with the chief complaints of diarrhea and sudden death in the flock noticed 3 days after stocking of the birds and a day prior to presentation. Further history revealed that the birds were purchased from a farm in Kaduna. Clinical examination was carried out on the live one and post mortem examination was conducted on the carcasses. The farm was visited and inspected; clinical signs observed were somnolence, nasal discharges, sinusitis, swollen heads and wattles, cyanosis of combs and wattles and their vents were soiled with yellowish feces. Avian Influenza (AI) was tentatively diagnosed, necessary samples were taken to National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom for analyses and the flock was treated symptomatically. Other animals (cattle, sheep, broiler chickens, pigeons and fish) were also reared in the farm. Two hundred and fifty five chickens died within four days. AI was confirmed at NVRI, Vom. The farm was depopulated and the premises decontaminated by fumigation. The conclusion was the hens were infected and incubating the disease from the farm they were purchased. It was recommended that the farmer should rest the farm for at least three months before restocking, always obtain birds from reputable and disease free source and strict biosecurity measures should be followed in managing the farm.

Key words: Avian Influenza, Layer Chickens, Outbreak, Sokoto

INTRODUCTION

Avian Influenza is a viral disease of almost all domestic and wild birds affecting the digestive, respiratory and nervous systems (Stallknecht and Shane, 1998). The disease is world-wide in distribution and the virus occurs naturally in domestic poultry and other bird and animal species (Stallknecht and Shane, 1998). Avian Influenza viruses are segmented negative-strand RNA viruses of the family *Orthomyxoviridae* having 3 genera which are Influenzavirus A, B and C. (Capua and Marangon, 2006). The only genus that causes natural infection in birds is Influenza A which is further divided to sub-types according to antigenic characteristics of Hemagglutinin (H) and Neuraminidase (N). The identified ones are H1-

H16 and N1-N9 and each virus has one H and one N antigen in any combination (Capua and Marangon, 2006). Influenza A virus is further divided into 2 distinct groups: Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) and Low Pathogenic Avian Influenza (LPAI). HPAI virus can cause severe disease with high mortality; it also disrupts poultry production and trade (Moris and Jackson, 2005). The loss of production caused by HPAI results in scarcity of poultry and its by products which consequently leads to increase in cost of poultry and poultry by products, affected countries stand the risk of losing right to export of such products (Abdu *et al.*, 2005).

In Nigeria, first outbreak of Avian Influenza (H5N1) was confirmed in 2006 in commercial poultry farm in Jaji Kaduna State in which the source is still not clear but it was assumed that international trade of birds and migratory birds could be responsible (Monne *et al.* 2008).

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The outbreak was not unexpected to the country considering the HPAI situation globally at that time. The Federal Government was prepared for possible emergency and had control strategies put in place (Agnes *et al.*, 2012). The virus later spread to commercial farms in several other states including Kano, Plateau, Katsina, Bauchi and other agro-ecological regions of the country killing over 1.2 million domesticated birds and many culled to stop its spread (Monne *et al.* 2008). Between 2006 and 2007, outbreaks were reported from Hanwa-Lowcost, Shika, Samaru, and Zango areas in Zaria Kaduna State, where 5,233 birds died out of 24,428 (Wakawa *et al.*, 2008). From 2006 to 2008, outbreaks of HPAI subtype H5N1 virus infection in poultry negatively affected the agricultural sector in Nigeria (WHO, 2007). Nwanko *et al.* (2012) reported 3 Avian influenza positive cases out of 221 apparently healthy birds from live bird market in Sokoto which were tested using nested polymerase chain reaction (nPCR). In 2015, the disease reoccurred in a commercial poultry farm and a live bird market in Kano and Lagos states respectively (WHO, 2007). A new strain of the Virus (H5N8) was reported in Kano State believed to be more pathogenic than H5N1 (WHO, 2007). In Nigeria, one human death as a result of AI was reported in January 2007 (WHO, 2007). The disease is still in Nigeria despite different control measures adopted to eradicate it. This is the first confirmed outbreak of Avian Influenza in Sokoto, Nigeria.

Case Report

On 7th March, 2016, the management of a farm in Kwannawa area Sokoto presented three (3) carcasses and one (1) live chicken to the Avian Ambulatory Clinic of the Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto from a flock of 956 19-week old Isa brown layers with chief complaints of diarrhea and sudden death in the flock noticed 3 days after stocking of the birds and a day prior to presentation. The birds were sourced from a farm in Kaduna state. Previous medications and vaccinations were not known to the farm management but the chickens were given Vitalyte[®] (multivitamin) powder in drinking water on arrival. They were kept in a deep litter house and fed with Vital[®] growers feed. Egg production was 12%. Four hens died in the first two days of stocking after manifesting some signs of illness including flu and diarrhea. Many died eventually, the percentage mortality before intervention was approximately 10%.

The presented chicken appeared dull and somnolent, bilateral serous nasal discharge, respiratory rales, and soiled vent were also observed.

Post mortem examination was carried out on the presented carcasses and the following were the findings:

- Presence of feed in the oral cavity 3/3
- Pale pectoral muscles (Moderate muscular pallor) 2/3
- Congested trachea (Severe hemorrhagic tracheitis) 1/3

- Cloudy air sacs (Moderate airsacculitis) 2/3
- Congested heart (Mild congestion) 1/3
- Haemorrhagic follicles (Moderate hemorrhagic oophoritis) 3/3
- Ballooned caeca (Moderate) 3/3

Key: Numerators are the number of chickens with observed lesions while denominators are the total number of chickens examined

The lesions are shown in plates 1-6 in the appendix.

The farm was visited and inspected. The feed and water troughs were found to be dirty. The farmer was practicing an integrated farming rearing sheep, cattle (both exotic and cross breeds), fish, broiler chickens and pigeons in the same farm. From the layers flock 36 hens were found to be somnolent with nasal discharges, sinusitis, conjunctivitis, swollen heads and wattles which were also cyanotic, their vents were soiled with yellowish feces and they were immediately isolated. 72 were found dead. Some of the clinical manifestations are shown in plates 7 and 8 in the appendix. Post mortem examination was again conducted on 7 carcasses with the following findings.

- Severe hemorrhagic tracheitis - 4/7
- Moderate hemorrhagic tracheitis - 3/7
- Moderate muscular pallor-2/7
- Severe airsacculitis -2/7
- Moderate airsacculitis - 1/7
- Moderate haemorrhages of the proventriculus -2/7
- Moderate ballooning of duodenum -1/7
- Severe Haemorrhages of spleen -2/7
- Severe haemorrhagic enteritis -3/7
- Severe haemorrhage at ileocaecal junction - 2/7
- Moderate ballooning of caecum 3/7
- Severe congestion of the follicles in 4/7

Key: Numerators are the number of chickens with observed lesions while denominators are the total number of chickens examined. Some of the post mortem lesions are shown in plates 9 and 10 in the appendix.

Diagnosis: The clinical signs and post mortem lesions were suggestive of Avian Influenza. The situation was reported to the Sokoto State Avian Influenza desk officer from State zonal Veterinary Clinic; he visited the farm, took and sent sera and oropharyngeal swab samples to National Veterinary Research Institute (N.V.R.I) Vom Plateu state for Avian Influenza investigation. Serum samples from five moribund chickens were taken for Newcastle Disease investigation by Hemagglutination inhibition test, so also tracheal and cloacal swabs for bacterial culture and sensitivity tests in Faculty of Veterinary Medicine UDUS. Symptomatic treatment was done before obtaining laboratory results viz:

- Intergendox[®] water soluble powder (100mg gentamicin sulphate 50mg doxycycline hyclate) 100g in 150L of

drinking water x 5/7.

- Vitalyte[®] water soluble powder 30g in 40L of drinking water x5/7. On 9th March, 2016, 179 hens died.

RESULT

Avian Influenza results: The farm received result from (N.V.R.I) Vom confirming Avian Influenza.

Serology: Hemagglutination inhibition test result showed antibody titre for Newcastle disease to range from log₂⁴ to log₂⁵ in the sera of 5 chickens tested.

Microbiology results: Tracheal swab: Culture yielded the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* after 24 hours of incubation aerobically at 37°C.

Sensitive to: Ofloxacin, Gentamicin, Nitrofurantoin.

Resistance to: Amoxicillin, Augmentin, Cotrimoxazole.

Cloacal swab: Culture yielded the growth of *Enterobacter species* after 24 hours of incubation aerobically at 37°C.

Sensitive to: Nalidixic acid, Gentamycin, Ofloxacin, Nitrofurantoin.

Resistance to: Tetracycline, Amoxicillin, Cotrimoxazole.

All the birds in the farm were disposed off on 13/03/2016 and the poultry houses were cleaned and disinfected (plate 11 in the appendix). The ambulatory team was shown in plate 12 of the appendix.

DISCUSSION

The outbreak of Avian influenza in Sokoto signified persistence of the virus in Nigeria. The re-emergence showed difficulty in controlling the disease despite different control measures embarked upon. It could also be believed that more birds especially poultry in Kaduna state are still harboring the virus and continue to be source of introduction of the disease to different parts of the country as it was in the first outbreak. All viruses are introduced to domestic poultry primarily through direct or indirect contact with infected birds. In this case, the introduction of new birds into the farm which was housing healthy birds of different species and breeds without ascertaining the history and health status of the newly stocked birds, lead to problem of introduction of the highly pathogenic avian influenza disease consequently resulting to the depopulation of the farm and causing serious economic loss to the farmer. There was concurrent infection with Newcastle disease virus, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Enterobacter species*. The bacterial infection is possibly due to lowering of immunity as a result of the viral infection. Antibody titre protective standard for birds against Newcastle disease is log₂⁴ (OIE, 2012).

CONCLUSION

The conclusion was that the hens were infected and

incubating the Avian Influenza Virus from the farm they were sourced, causing highly pathogenic avian influenza disease. Avian Influenza is still re-emerging causing threat to poultry production in Nigeria. Also Kaduna state is still not free of Avian influenza. Antibodies to Newcastle disease were seen to be high which could be due to natural infection or vaccination.

RECOMMENDATION

It was recommended that the farmer should rest the farm for at least three months before restocking, strict biosecurity measures should be followed in managing the farm and farmers should always maintain good sanitary condition of their farms as the virus could be transmitted via contaminated equipment, fomites, vehicles and infectious organic materials. Professional advice should always be solicited by farmers before sourcing birds to enable obtaining birds from reputable and disease free farms.

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APPENDIX

Plate 1. Muscular pallor

Plate 2. Congested trachea

Plate 3. Ballooned ceca

Plate 4. Hemorrhagic follicles

Plate 5. Cloudy air sac

Plate 6. Congested heart

Plate 7: Nasal dischargeconjunctivitis,

Plate 8: A layer exhibiting respiratory distress swollen head and cyanoticwattles

Plate 9: Hemorrhages at ileocecal

Plate10: Petechial hemorrhage of the junction proventriculus

Plate 11: Depopulated poultry pen

Plate 12: Ambulatory team